

Comparison of thermographic, EEG and subjective measures of affective experience of designed stimuli.

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Abstract

This paper reports on work undertaken to establish the efficacy of Infrared Thermography (IRT) as an accurate, non-contact measurement tool for studying user experience during product interaction. IRT was compared with two other established methods of measuring changes of emotional state; Electroencephalogram (EEG) and Affective Self Report (ASR). Sixteen male undergraduate designers were given a cognitive task whilst simultaneous IRT and EEG measurements were made. ASR measures of Arousal and Valence were recorded along with an additional post test scale for Task Engagement. Using the Pearson product-moment correlation, a strong positive association was established between changes in forehead temperature and changes in total EEG activity between baseline and test condition. A negative correlation was established between EEG and some dimensions of affect. No correlation was observed between IRT and ASR measures for the sample, however, individual differences observed suggest that temperature dynamics may be associated with the intensity of affective state change.

Conference theme: Usage & Interaction

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Introduction

There is a need for design researchers to move beyond the limitations of subjective interpretations of 'design and emotion' and explore the use of new tools and multi-modal methods in the objective measurement of human experience (Love, 2004, ENGAGE, 2005).

Recent theories in the field of neuroscience propose that emotions play an essential part in our cognitive processes and decision making (Bechara & Damasio, 2005). These developments have identified the importance of the role that the body and our 'sense' of our body may play in defining our conscious mind and sense of 'self'. These theories relate emotion, feeling and consciousness to the body and state the significance of the physiological and neurological somatosensory systems that monitor and control its stability (Damasio, 2000). The suggestion that emotion is a key part of the mechanism of homeostasis and that this mechanism is in turn pivotal in shaping our experience of the world around us is an important one in relation to the further development of tools for the objective measurement of affective experience. The human body is a thermo-regulatory system and human skin, the largest organ, plays a key role in the regulation of body temperature. Regional skin temperature dynamics reflect the internal condition of the body and have been used extensively in medicine to study and monitor the health status of the individual. On this basis, it is possible to hypothesise that changes in temperature dynamics may also be a reflection of changes in the affective status of the individual, and as such these changes may be used as a metric of user / product interaction.

There are a variety of physiological measures, such as skin conductance, heart rate (HR) and blood pressure (BP), which have been used extensively in psychophysiological studies of emotion. These relate specifically to the activities of the autonomic nervous system (ANS). It is significant that measures relating to vascular activity, particularly HR and BP (Waldstein et al., 2000) are 'tried and tested' metrics and have been used in parallel with Electroencephalogram (EEG) measures. Research methods focus on the measurement of specific ANS activity (Christie & Friedman, 2004) and there is increasing evidence of '*emotional patterning*' in ANS activity relating to specific affective states (Vianna & Tranel, 2005). The main drawback of current techniques is their varying levels of invasiveness which place limitations on experimental methods, particularly when exploring user/product interaction. IRT is a highly accurate method of measuring changes in skin temperature arising from vasodilation and constriction (Ring & Ammer, 2000); it is proposed that this non-invasive method may be sensitive enough to be used as an objective measure of a subject's affective response to designed stimuli.

To date there has been limited exploration of the use of thermal imaging in the analysis of human interaction with products on a physical level, for example user comfort (McCloone et al., 2000) and no evidence of its use to analyse other facets of human-product interaction, specifically changes in affective state. As a tool for medical and ergonomic research, thermography has been used to analyse various physical conditions but there is a dearth of information relating to its application in psychophysiological studies, particularly in studies of emotion. Some researchers have begun to address this (Merla & Romani, 2007, Pavlidis et al., 2005) while at the same time asymmetry in facial blood flow and temperature have been linked to reported lateralized experience of emotion in the brain (Benedicic et al., 2006).

Recently published work outlined an investigation into the potential use of Infrared Thermography (IRT) as an accurate, non-contact measurement tool for use in studying user experience during product interaction (Jenkins et al., 2007). This work demonstrated that there were significant changes in facial temperature dynamics of subjects engaged in puzzle-solving activity and that these can be accurately measured using IRT. Based on theories positing a relationship between vascular blood flow and affective state (Adelmann & Zajonc, 1989, McIntosh et al., 1997, Zajonc, 1985, Zajonc et al., 1989), the premise of this work was that the observed temperature changes at the region of interest, in this case the forehead, arise from a combination of cognitive and emotional psychophysical effects. Puzzle-solving was selected as it could be viewed both as a representation of the activity of designing and of interaction with a complex product; both requiring a degree of cognitive work, physical action and affective state change.

To establish the efficacy of IRT as a measurement tool for the analysis of affective experiences during user/product interaction it is important to establish a correlation between other accepted measures used in emotion research. If a positive relationship can be established between IRT and EEG it would further support the proposal that facial temperature dynamics are a reflection of internal 'states of mind'. Frontal EEG is an established method of measuring both emotional and cognitive functions. There is a substantial body of scientific literature exploring the relationship between frontal EEG asymmetry and emotion which provides a useful framework for evaluating the IRT findings (Allen et al., 2004, Cacioppo, 2004, Davidson, 2004). Like EEG, IRT can provide a record of change in the subject's state in real time; therefore, comparisons can be made between modalities both as a function of time and in relation to known patterns of frontal cortex activity as a correlate of affective state. Many studies have related left side activation to positive emotions and approach behaviors, and right side

activation to negative emotion and withdrawal behaviors (e.g. Coan & Allen, 2004).

Triangulation with an Affective Self Report (ASR) should provide insight into a subject's perceptions or 'feelings' of their experience thus helping to establish what it is that IRT may be measuring.

Experimental Method:

Experimental Stimuli:

A key issue in the development of the experimental method was the format for the experimental stimulus. A variety of techniques have been used in psychophysiological studies to elicit an emotional response, however, there is evidence to suggest that stronger affective responses are elicited when subjects are required to engage in personal recall tasks (Waldstein et al., 2000). Also, recently published models of user-product interaction refer to three types of interaction with products; Instrumental, Non-Instrumental and Non-Physical (Desmet & Hekkert, 2007). They suggest that at the non-physical level thinking about or anticipating use may stimulate affective response. Due to the experimental limitations of EEG, specifically the interference created by physical movement of the subject, it was decided to focus on the non-physical level of interaction and simulate 'thinking about' using products to perform a task.

The test stimulus consisted of a modified version of the 'Zoo Map Test'. This test is part of a battery of psychological tests (BADs – Behavioural Assessment of the Dysexecutive Syndrome) (Wilson et al., 1996) designed to assess executive function. Subjects are required to formulate a route around a map of a fictitious zoo, without contravening a set of rules. A common everyday activity – making a hot drink – was selected to ensure there would be a high degree of familiarity for test subjects. The variation designed for this experiment required the subject to read the instructions on-screen (see below), visualise using the depicted products to perform the activity and formulate a route accordingly. Although certain rules were stipulated subjects were able to formulate the plan independently. This was intended to create a higher demand condition and allow a degree of flexibility so each individual's schema for the task was influential. Subjects were asked not to verbalise their thoughts and to trace out their route on the map in their mind as it was presented on screen (Figure 1). This 'map' was designed to prompt a higher degree of engagement and, it was hypothesised, would stimulate cognitive activity by demanding the subject's active consideration of their interactions with the products presented in the map. The test comprised of a two minute baseline rest period, followed by a two minute period of stimulus presentation, followed by a further two minute rest period. The on screen instructions were as follows:

Tea or Coffee? Imagine you are going to make a hot drink for yourself...

1. Look carefully at all the objects below.
2. Think carefully about the order you would use them.
3. Visualise how you would use them to make your drink.

You may decide which drink you would prefer but you must obey the following rules:

- If you **choose tea** you must **use the teapot only**. If you **choose coffee** you must **use the coffee pot only**. You must **use all the other objects**.
- You **must add milk and sugar**. You **may use the spoon as many times as you like**.
- Take your time. If you finish and the image is still on screen choose the other drink and repeat the task.

Figure 1: 'Map' test stimulus

Affective Self Report (ASR)

Several studies of emotion combining physiological and self reporting methods (Vianna & Tranel, 2005, Christie & Friedman, 2004 and Neumann & Waldstein, 2001) were considered in the design of the Affective Self Report (ASR) measures for this experiment. A number of approaches have been used including discrete emotions and dimensional models of affect and it is the latter which has been cited by Desmet & Hekkert as a more appropriate model when considering peoples affective state during product interactions. The ASR measures of the

Arousal and Valence dimensions were recorded using two five item scales. Waldstein et al. (2000) have used an additional measure of Task Engagement when comparing EEG and other physiological measures with emotional recall tasks. An additional four item scale for the level of Engagement with the task was incorporated in to the post test questionnaire. Each item comprised of a bi-polar pair of adjectives selected to be consistent with the literature previously mentioned (Table 1). Subjects were asked to place a mark on a 10cm line how they felt at that time. A baseline measure was recorded after acclimatisation and immediately before the test conditions were implemented. A second measure was recorded immediately after the test was complete. Mean scores for each scale were calculated. Baseline scores were subtracted from the post test scores to provide a measure of each individual's perceived affective state change for Arousal (ΔA) and Valence (ΔV). These change scores were also combined to provide a measure of Total Affect ($\Delta A + \Delta V$).

Items reflecting affective dimensions;

VALENCE	Pleasant	Unpleasant
	Satisfied	Disappointed
	Irritated	Content
	Annoyed	Pleased
	Unhappy	Happy
AROUSAL	Relaxed	Tense
	Patient	Anxious
	Curious	Indifferent
	Energetic	Tired
	Restless	Calm

Items reflecting task engagement;

ENGAGEMENT	Simple	Difficult
	Frustrating	Satisfying
	Challenging	Easy
	Agreeable	Disagreeable

Table 1: ASR Scales. Items were counterbalanced and randomized.

EEG Equipment and protocols:

EEG data was recorded from specific locations according to the International 10-20 electrode placement system. The locations for the scalp electrodes were F3 and F4, reference electrodes were placed on each ipsilateral earlobe and a ground electrode placed at Cz. Impedances was

below 5Hz. The hardware used to record the EEG was a NeuroAmp, with a data acquisition rate of 1000 samples per second and a sampling rate of 250Hz.

IRT Equipment and protocols:

An internally cooled Cedip Infrared Systems Titanium 560 camera with a 25mm (FOV 21°) optical lens was used in the experiment. The camera has a 640x512 / 14 bit detector focal plane array. The camera's Indium Antimonide (InSb) sensor is highly sensitive to the shortwave infrared spectral band (3.4 – 5 μm). The camera was connected to a DELL Precision M60 Workstation laptop via a Camlink interface for digital video capture. Although capable of capturing images at a maximum full frame rate of up to 380Hz the capture rate and image size were reduced to two frames per second at 320x256 to minimize file sizes. The images were directly acquired and subsequently analysed using Cedip's Altair v5.8 software. Motion compensation was undertaken in a post processing module. The thermal imaging camera was situated at eye level directly in front of the subjects at a fixed distance of 1.5m.

A flexible plastic template with a grid of holes at 5mm intervals was used to 'mark-up' the subject's forehead with a metallic ink pen which would be visible in the thermal images due to its different emissivity properties. Eight reference points were marked to enable post-process motion compensation and ensure accurate and consistent positioning of measurement tools defining Regions of Interest (ROI) in subsequent thermal image analysis. To accommodate the anthropometric variation in forehead dimensions the same method was used for each subject: the centreline of the forehead was defined with two points, one positioned just above the nasion - a recessed point between the forehead and nose - to a point below the hairline. The outer edge of the eyes were used to define a further set of three reference points indicating the pronounced transition in surface plane direction of the forehead (frontal bone) along the temporal line. This demarcation ensured that the ROI's were placed on anterior surfaces only during analysis. The mean temperature of the Right and Left ROI's were used to produce timing graphs of temperature change over the 320 second (720 frames) sequence. The temperature scales of the thermal images were 'squeezed' to a 2°C span to highlight temperature distribution. (Figure 2)

Figure 2: Gray scale and ROYGBIV palettes applied to thermal images.

Experimental Procedure:

Sixteen male volunteers (mean age=21.75 years) from the undergraduate degree portfolio of the School of Industrial Design participated in the experiment which had been approved by the University Ethics Committee. All subjects were fully briefed and signed a consent form prior to their participation in the experiment. Biographical and anthropometric data were recorded before beginning the experiment. The subject was then seated in a comfortable, high backed chair facing a Dell 18" TFT display and the thermal imaging camera. The repeatability and reliability of thermal imaging is an area of key concern in medicine and appropriate standards have been established to produce reliable and valid results (Ring, et al, 2007). Due cognisance has been given to these recommendations for good practice in this research work. A period of ten minutes was allowed for briefing and instrumentation of the subjects, a further ten minute period was allowed for acclimatisation to the ambient conditions and experimental equipment.

Baseline signals were subtracted from the test signals for both IRT and EEG to provide a measure of state change for right (ΔR) and left sides (ΔL). Asymmetry was calculated by subtracting the left from right ($\Delta R - \Delta L$). The Pearson product-moment (r) correlation was used in the analysis of the data obtained from IRT, EEG and ASR across the sample group. Levels of significance for a two-tailed test were used as no assumptions were made about the direction of change in the test measures.

Results:

A summary of the correlations provided by the preliminary statistical analysis of the IRT, EEG and ASR data is given below (Table 2).

	IRT (ΔR)	IRT (ΔL)	IRT Asym. ($\Delta R - \Delta L$)	Arousal (ΔA)	Valence (ΔV)	Total Affect ($\Delta A + \Delta V$)	Task Engagement
IRT (ΔR)	~	~	~	-0.18	-0.07	-0.28	-0.01
IRT (ΔL)	~	~	~	-0.15	-0.00	-0.18	-0.06
IRT Asym. ($\Delta R - \Delta L$)	~	~	~	-0.09	-0.11	-0.20	0.07
EEG (ΔR)	0.50	~	~	-0.64	-0.03	-0.79	-0.18
EEG (ΔL)	~	0.63	~	-0.66	0.18	-0.63	-0.09
EEG Asym. ($\Delta R - \Delta L$)	~	~	-0.04	-0.34	0.32	-0.11	0.06

Table 2: Summary of triangulation results. (*r* indicates values where $p \leq 0.05$)

The results of the linear correlation carried out for the IRT and EEG indicate a strong positive association between change in temperature (ΔT) and change in total EEG (ΔE) activity from baseline to test condition for the map stimulus. This positive correlation was observed for both the right and left sides (Right: $r = 0.497$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.05$ Left: $r = 0.633$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.01$). A Scatter plot of the data indicates a potential outlier (Figure 3). If the outlier is removed from the data set the level of significance increases to $p \leq 0.01$ for the Right side and $p \leq 0.001$ for the Left side.

Figure 3: Relationship between temperature change ($^{\circ}C$) and change in total EEG (μ) activity.

No correlation was observed in Right | Left asymmetry between IRT and EEG signals. IRT shows no significant correlation with the individual dimensions of Arousal, Valence or Task

Engagement. There appears to be a weak negative association between IRT and the Total Affect measure but this is below significant levels.

The results also indicate a strong negative correlation between change in total EEG (ΔE) activity and change in Arousal (ΔA) for both the right and left sides (Right: $r = -0.64$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.01$ Left: $r = -0.66$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.01$). Similarly, a strong negative correlation is seen between EEG and change in Total Affect ($\Delta A + \Delta V$) for both sides (Right: $r = -0.79$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.001$ Left: $r = -0.63$, $N=16$, $p \leq 0.01$). There is no apparent relationship between EEG (ΔE) and Valence (ΔV) or Task Engagement. EEG Right | Left asymmetry shows a weaker negative association with Arousal and a weak positive association with Valence but these are below significant values. No correlation is exhibited between EEG asymmetry and Total Affect.

The mean ASR scores for the dimensions of Arousal and Valence for the baseline were subtracted from scores for the Map stimulus to provide a measure of change in affective state. A strong negative linear correlation was observed between Arousal and Valence ($r = -0.56$, $N=16$, $P \leq 0.05$). Again, it is noticeable in the scatter plot that the same subject is a potential outlier (Figure 4). Removal from the data set increases the correlation to $r = -0.59$.

Figure 4: Relationship between change in affective dimensions of Arousal and Valence.

As stated, IRT shows no significant correlation with the ASR measures across the sample group. However, comparison of trends in temperature change with ASR measures on a per subject basis indicate pronounced increase in temperature when subjects reported greater negative valence and increased arousal. The figure below illustrates the comparative differences in temperature trends at the ROI between Subject 03 and Subject 12 whose relative positions in the

scatter plot are highlighted in Figure 4 above. There was noticeable asymmetry in both temperature and raw EEG signals although no linear correlation was observed between these variables within the sample. However, it is clear in the example of subject 03 that although both right and left temperatures follow the same trend the right side shows a greater relative increase. This does parallel those previously identified traits in frontal cortex activity for negative emotion and raises further discussion points. This comparison exemplifies the positive correlations established in the statistical analysis and also indicates a potential relationship between temperature dynamics and the nature and intensity of affective experiences.

Figure 5: Timing graph comparison of temperature trends for Subject 03 and 12.

Discussion:

Analysis of the IRT signal data suggests that for the sample, no significant change was induced by the map stimulus, however, pronounced individual differences were observed in IRT, EEG and ASR measures. In the case of subject 03, identified previously, a marked increase in temperature was also paralleled by increased Arousal and negative Valence. Those subjects that exhibited more stable temperature profiles also demonstrated a more apparent degree of stability in ASR and EEG measures. The distribution of data points in the Arousal vs. Valence

scatter plot clearly illustrates this observation, with the subject exhibiting the most pronounced change in temperature also being located furthest from equilibrium point in the *negative|aroused* quadrant of the affective space. The apparent ‘clustering’ of many subjects around the equilibrium point suggests that the ‘Map’ test stimulus did not elicit a high demand condition in the sample group as a whole, and therefore did not evoke significant affective state change. In light of these observations and the previously discussed proposal, made by Damasio, that emotion is an integral part of homeostasis it is possible to make several reasonable assumptions:

- The strength of an individual’s response to a stimulus (positive or negative) is reflected in the degree of measurable temperature change.
- The relatively balanced distribution of most of the subjects between the *negative|aroused* and the *positive|calm* quadrants and their proximity to the equilibrium point of the affective space suggests that (1) the stimulus did not evoke a strong enough emotional response, (2) a neutral response to a stimulus may be characterised by a steady thermal state.
- If the task had created a higher demand condition then it may have produced a significant association between IRT and ASR measures for the sample group and not just individuals within the group.
- ASR appears to be dependant on an individual’s sensitivity to their own ‘feelings’. Where there is significant change in temperature there is also significant change in reported affective state. This suggests that ASR may require gross changes in affective state for conscious awareness and accurate report. This also suggests that IRT could provide a useful measure of individual perceptions of a stimulus in relation to the strength of the evoked response.

The sample group was limited to all male design undergraduates so we cannot assume it is representative of the population. The focus on male participants only was deliberate to remove any influence that gender may have as a variable. There appear to be two ‘types’ of group within the sample demonstrating contrasting temperature asymmetry characteristics. For the ROI used, half the sample group exhibited right dominant asymmetry, six exhibited left dominance and two exhibited no significant asymmetry at rest. The relationship between IRT and EEG asymmetry clearly requires more investigation. Raw EEG activity is a reflection of overall brain activity (in this case 2 – 38 Hz) and does not provide a detailed measure of emotional state. Further comparison between IRT signals and the different EEG frequencies associated with emotion is required to add depth to our understanding of this relationship.

Furthermore, current experimental techniques have used anatomical sites identified in earlier work of Zajonc. Recent work of previously cited researchers such as Pavlidis and Merla suggests alternative facial ROI's which warrant further investigation.

Conclusions:

The objective of the experiment was to establish a relationship between IRT and EEG during a cognitive task. The results presented clearly demonstrate that there are strong positive correlations between changes in forehead temperature and changes in total EEG activity for the sample group. This adds considerable support to the hypothesis that changes in temperature dynamics may reflect changes in the affective status of the individual, and as such these changes may be used as a metric of user/product interaction.

No significant associations were observed between temperature change and ASR measures for the sample, however, there were correlations observed between these measures and total EEG activity. It is noticeable that in those isolated cases where the task triggered a significant affective response there was a pronounced change in temperature. On this basis it can be hypothesized that the apparent gap in triangulation may be due to the strength of the stimulus. It is also important to note that EEG's sensitivity to movement limited the experimental stimulus to the non-physical level of interaction. Physical levels of user/product interaction bring additional somatosensory systems in to play which, on the basis of current theories in neuroscience, it can be assumed would add to the intensity of the individual's experiences.

The literature suggests a strong relationship exists between frontal EEG asymmetry and emotion. Noticeable differences in temperature asymmetry traits were observed indicating the apparent existence of two 'types' within the sample. Although asymmetry was also observed in EEG measures no correlation has currently been established for the sample and further work is required to investigate this relationship.

The work presented makes considerable progress in establishing the viability of IRT as a tool for studying user/product interaction. The link established with EEG activity clearly demonstrates its potential for use in design usability research and future work is intended to explore the causal relationships between facial temperature dynamics, cognitive demand and affective experiences.

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